

Work Package 6, Milestone 6.4: Query interface for complexes

Work Package 6, Milestone 6.4: Query interface for complexes	1
Introduction.....	2
CAPRI organization.....	2
Bound/Unbound targets	3
Previous CAPRI targets	3
Evaluation meetings.....	5
Evaluation criteria.....	6
Outlook	6
User requirements for query system	6
Implementation plan.....	8
References	9

Milestone M24

Introduction

Most proteins act in concert with other proteins, forming permanent or transient complexes. Understanding these interactions at an atomic level is only possible through analysis of protein structures. The query system for complexes aims to offer a search system of complexes comprising of both predicted and experimentally established structures of complexes, the former provided by the result of the CAPRI (Critical Assessment of PRredicted Interactions) experiment, while the latter provided by annotation of complexes provided in the PDB and EMDB data archives and value added data on complexes at PDBe . These complexes are composed of biomacromolecules e.g. protein–protein complexes, protein-nucleic acid complexes, or protein-sugar complexes. Designed complexes are also valid for the query system. Some of these complexes fall into the realm of integrative/hybrid methods, as they integrate experimental data from multiple methods. In CAPRI, additional data such as SAS profiles have been provided before.

The PDB contains experimentally-determined structures of complexes that can be queried based on assembly composition. Some of these compositions are “protein-protein complex”, “RNA/protein complex”, “DNA/protein complex”, DNA/DNA/RNA hybrid complex” and others. In addition, the search system also allows grouping and faceting based on the assembly polymer count and whether the assembly is a homo/hetero assembly which allows users to search for entries with assembly compositions such as hetero dimer, homo trimer, tetramer, and so on. In addition, PDBePISA, which is hosted by EMBL-EBI, provides the automatic detection of macromolecular assemblies in the PDB solved by X-ray crystallography. Thus, entries that are likely to form a complex in solution could be determined using this program.

For predicted complexes, such query system does not exist; hence development of methods for complex prediction does not have the necessary support infrastructure. The large amount of data on predicted complexes from the CAPRI prediction round results can help in supporting methodology development. The CAPRI complex prediction experiment was designed in 2000 to test protein docking algorithms in blind predictions of the structure of protein complexes. In 17 years, 130 complexes (called CAPRI ‘targets’) have been subjected to structure prediction by docking their two components. CAPRI relies on the willingness of structural biologists to provide unpublished experimental structures as targets. Each round typically sees no less than 30 groups participating, consisting of both server and human teams.

The aim of CAPRI is to test protein-protein docking prediction methods and algorithms, and assess the validity of the predictions made by different programs and groups. Another objective of CAPRI is to test the capacity of protein-protein docking programs to produce meaningful biological information, especially to predict modes of association which can be useful guides for genetic and biochemical experiments.

CAPRI organization

CAPRI is organized based on ‘rounds’ - a round can be organized whenever an experimentalist offers an adequate target. At the start of a round, registered predictor groups are given sequence or atomic coordinates for the components of a complex, and the round ends six to eight weeks later with the submission of predicted structures. Each round is divided into a prediction and scoring experiment. Prediction round involves groups and software called ‘predictor’ who predict the model poses for the complex, whereas the scoring round involves groups called ‘scorer’ who mainly develop scoring algorithms for predicted complexes.

Milestone M24

Predictor groups are allowed to submit up to 100 models of each target to be assessed. In addition, they are invited to upload larger sets of models that are used in a scoring experiment immediately following the prediction. At the end of the round, the predictors' submissions are assessed by comparison to the X-ray structure. The scorer groups have a few days to rerank the uploaded models and make their own 10 model submissions. The predictions are thus made blindly, without any knowledge of the correct answer, and the evaluation is carried out by an independent team from whom the identity of the predictors is concealed.

CAPRI rounds are conducted and managed on the CAPRI Web site (<http://capri.ebi.ac.uk/>) hosted by the European Bioinformatics Institute. The Web site has been the major method of communication between the management group and the predictors since the first round of CAPRI. All the information on the targets are given through a passworded section of the Web site, and all predictions are deposited there.

Bound/Unbound targets

Not all soon-to-be-released protein complexes are valid targets for CAPRI: the component structures, or at least a homolog from which the model could be derived from, must be known independently. Predictors are only given sequences of the target, which they can use to search for an appropriate starting model or build a homologous model. Taking a complex apart and reconstructing it in the computer is known as "bound" docking. It is a useful computational exercise to test programs but not a realistic problem. In bound docking, the two components are frozen in their bound conformation. A lock-and-key fit is achieved only when the components are provided in the right orientation and position, which very much biases the prediction. "Unbound" docking starts from the two independently determined protein structures. Therefore, it must handle the conformational changes that are inevitable on association and make docking a far more difficult task than just searching for an exact fit. Thus, the "unbound" docking prediction is the most ideal situation for a CAPRI experiment. However, "bound/unbound" complexes between a protein of known structure and a novel protein are also acceptable, which is important as The Protein Data Bank[ref] contains only a few dozen systems for which the complex and its two component proteins have had their structure independently determined.

Previous CAPRI targets

Examples of previous targets can be seen in the tables below, taken from past CAPRI publications.

Milestone M24

Table 2. Overview of the prediction quality for 17 CAPRI targets

Target	Reference	Submitting groups	Model quality ^a		
			High/good	Acceptable	
T01	HPr kinase/HPr	Fioulaine et al. 2002	16	0	8
T02 ^b	Rotavirus VP6/Fab	Thouvenin et al. 2001	15	1	6
T03	Flu hemagglutinin/Fab	Barbey-Martin et al. 2002	13	2	0
T04	Amylase/camel V _{HH}	Desmyter et al. 2002	13	0	0
T05	Amylase/camel V _{HH}	Desmyter et al. 2002	13	0	0
T06	Amylase/camel V _{HH}	Desmyter et al. 2002	13	8	0
T07 ^c	Superantigen/TCRβ	Sundberg et al. 2002	14	12	8
T08	Nidogen/laminin	Takagi et al. 2003	18	11	18
T09	LicT dimer	H. van Tilbeurgh and M. Graille, in prep.	17	0	0
T10	TBE virus E trimer	Bressanelli et al. 2004	20	1	3
T11	Cohesin/dockerin (<i>unbound</i>)	Carvalho et al. 2004	19	0	13
T12	Cohesin/dockerin (<i>bound</i>)	Carvalho et al. 2004	22	20	10
T13	SAG1/Fab	M. Graille and F. Ducancel, in prep.	21	5	8
T14	Phosphatase 1δ/MYPT1	Terrak et al. 2004	25	38	32
T15 ^d	Colicin D/Imm D	Graille et al. 2004	10	9	6
T18 ^e	Xylanase/TAXI	Sansen et al. 2004	26	5	4
T19	Ovine prion/Fab	Eghiaian et al. 2004	24	11	9

Source: (Janin, et al., 2003)

Table 1. The Targets of Rounds 6–12

Target	Complex	PDB code	Reference	Biological Function	Type ^a	Prediction Quality ^b
T20	HemK/RF1	2b3t	Graille et al., (2005)	Translation termination	UH	acceptable
T21	Orc1/Sir1	1zhi	Hou et al., (2005)	Transcription regulation	UU	medium
T22	U5-15k/U5-52k	1syx	Nielsen et al., (2007)	RNA splicing	UU	acceptable ^c
T23	hGBP1 dimer	2b8w	Ghosh et al., (2006)	Signal transduction	Q	incorrect ^c
T24	Arf1/ARHGAP21	2j59	Ménétrety et al., (2007)	Signal transduction	UH	acceptable
T25					UB	high
T26	TolB/Pal	2hqs	Bonsor et al., (2007)	Membrane transport	UU	medium
T27.1	HIP2/Ubc9	2o25	Walker et al., personal communication ^d	Protein processing	UU	incorrect
T27.2						medium
T28	NEDD4L dimer	2oni	Walker et al., personal communication ^e	Protein processing	Q	incorrect

Source: (Janin, 2007)

Table I

The Targets of Rounds 20–27

Target	Complex	Target type	PDB code	Reference
T43–45	Designed complexes	Affinity prediction	3R2X	[19]
T46	Mtq2/Trm112 methyltransferase	Homology	3Q87	[3]
T47	Colicin E2 DNase/Im2	Water positions	3U43	[10]
T48	T4moC/T4moH	Unbound	4I57	[5]
T49	T4moC/T4moH	Unbound	4I57	[5]
T50	HB36.3 design/flu HA	Unbound	3R2X	[15]
T51	Xylanase CtXyl5A	Multi-domain	4BXG	[7]
T52	–	Cancelled	–	–
T53	Rep4/Rep2 designs	Unbound	4JW2	[14]
T54	Neocarzinostatin/Rep16	Unbound	4JW3	[14]
T55–56	Designed complexes	Affinity prediction	4EEF	[21]
T57	BT4661 protein/heparin	Polysaccharide complex	4AK2	[8]
T58	PliG/SalG	Unbound, SAXS	4G9S	[4]

Source: (Janin, 2013)

Table 1. Targets of CAPRI Rounds 28–35

CAPRI Target ID	Protein and peptide names	PDB ID	Reference	Buried area (Å ²)	RMSD (Å) (Rec/Lig)	Seq-Identity (%)	Number of Residues
Protein–Peptide complexes							
T60	m-Importin- α /Gu- α	3zin	(¹)	1000	0.3/NA	100	426/15
T61	m-Importin- α /a28	3zio	(¹)	1000	0.3/NA	100	426/14
T62	m-Importin- α /a58	3zip	(¹)	1000	0.3/NA	100	426/14
T63	m-Importin- α /b6	3ziq	(¹)	1000	0.3/NA	100	426/14
T64	m-Importin- α /b141	3zir	(¹)	1000	0.3/NA	100	426/14
T65	RNase-H/SSB-Ct	4z0u	(²)	700	2.2/NA	100	155/10
T66	PriA DNA helicase/SSB-Ct	4n18	(³)	600	1.8/NA	100	550/10
T67	Nedd4 WW3/ PPxY ofARRDC3	4n7h	(⁴)	780	0.9/NA	100	33/13

Source: (Lensink, et al., 2017)

Evaluation meetings

Every 2-3 years, whenever a sufficient number of CAPRI targets have been assessed, the results are reviewed and the prediction performance of different groups is evaluated and discussed. Six CAPRI Evaluation Meetings have been held to discuss the outcome of CAPRI experiments. The results were reported in special issues of *Proteins*. During these meetings, the participants examine the docking predictions both in the context of individual targets and the success or failure of predictors to obtain good quality docking predictions. The quality of docking predictions (accurate/acceptable) are both quantified and the reasons are assessed.

Although each complex has features of its own that make the docking prediction easy or difficult, significant progress has been achieved in advancing our understanding of complex formation. Generally, how easy a given target to be predicted depends on how much the individual subunits undergo backbone readjustments upon complex formation. Targets that do not go through major conformational changes are easier to predict. It has been shown in previous CAPRI rounds that predictions are more likely to be of better quality when the targets have features in common with already-known and similar complexes, or the modes of binding have been seen before. In addition, if a complex involves building models of homo-oligomers, the quality of predictions depend greatly on whether or not the component has a homolog with an existing structure in the PDB. Success rate also depends on the size of the protein components, and the availability of supporting information from biochemical assays or from analyses on related proteins. Additionally, failures may be attributed to the participation of new predictor groups using novel algorithms.

Milestone M24

Evaluation criteria

The evaluation criteria to assess geometric and biological properties of the models depend on geometric fit, represented by the Irmsd and Lrmsd values, and contact residues, represented by the f(nat) value. Supposed that we call the larger component of a complex as R, and the other component as the ligand L, the Lrms distance is the distance between C-alpha atoms of L between the model and target, which is calculated after superposing the R of the model to the R of the target. Additionally, geometric quality can also be measured by the rotation angle rL and translation dL after the superimposition of model L to target L. The model geometry is also assessed based on Irms, the interface RMS distance, which is calculated of the C's of the epitopes only. Pairwise contacts between R and L residues are also used to judge the biological quality of the models. Additionally, the ratio of ligand contacts in the model to the ligand contacts in the target is calculated to measure how well the model predicts the epitopes, and the same is done for the receptor epitopes. The f(nat) value is calculated to measure which residues of R are in contact with which residues of L. In CAPRI assessment, the parameters Irms, Lrms, and f(nat) are combined to rank models into the categories 'incorrect', 'acceptable', 'medium' and 'high-quality'.

Outlook

Progress in the prediction quality observed from the past CAPRI rounds indicates that the experiment is a powerful incentive to develop new procedures that allow for flexibility during docking and incorporation of nonstructural information. Prediction methods based on protein-protein docking now produce reliable structural models when the conformation changes are small. Sorting out false positives and simulating large conformational changes remain a challenge, but predictor groups are actively developing better scoring functions and methods to reproduce the backbone movements and hinge rotations that accompany protein-protein interaction. The CAPRI experiment very much contributes to these developments.

However, even though the CAPRI experiment has so far produced a good amount of output especially with regards to docking performances, the structural biology community can not at present search through this data. Thus, there is a real need for such query mechanism. The CAPRI output could be useful for downstream strategic planning and development of docking algorithms, as well as for general users to gauge which server or human group predict certain types of complexes better, and thus could potentially benefit from collaborations or using the server for their own research projects.

User requirements for query system

This draft of user requirements is produced based on input from several members of the CAPRI management committee and previous participants of CAPRI rounds. Querying CAPRI results should be allowed at two different levels, namely, querying based on individual target, and querying based on individual participant (either scorer or predictor).

Based on individual target, users of the query system should be able to query based on (but not limited to) these criteria:

- Target number in CAPRI
- Round number in CAPRI

Milestone M24

- Round date
- Target/complex name
 - Receptor name
 - Ligand name
- Resolution
- PDB ID of published target
- Interface area
- Residue contacts
- Nonpolar/polar/charged composition
- Biochemical information (including stoichiometry of the target)
- Reference associated with the target
- Number of submitting groups for each target
 - Name of submitting groups
- Best performing group for each target
- Total number of model submission per target
- Model quality - 'incorrect', 'acceptable', 'medium' and 'high-quality'
- The number of native interface residues
- List of residues at the interface, defined by the CAPRI cutoff
- The number of non-native interface residues
- Clash threshold, average, standard deviation
- f(nat), f(non-nat), L-rms, i-rms, nclash
- Recall & precision level (e.g for 'medium' quality targets: <50%, for 'accurate' targets: >50%)
- Type of target- Homology/Multi-domain, Bound, Unbound, etc
 - Does the target mainly pose a homology modelling challenge or a docking challenge
- List of residues used to compute the superimpositions of all the models, i.e the residues common to all the models and the target
- List of interface residues of target
- Type of challenge: protein-ligand, protein-protein, protein-DNA etc...
- Number of components
- Target coordinate

Querying based on participating groups would be beneficial to know groups that produced correct predictions for all targets/rounds they have participated in. It would also be useful to distinguish predictions made by servers or by human groups, as generally servers display lower performance in docking predictions than manual submissions, including those by the developers of the same servers. Thus a query system would allow performance to be grouped based on the predictor type, allowing pattern of quality prediction to be gauged. Perhaps more importantly, since different groups are associated with different or specific methods, querying based on participants would allow users to identify if a specific method is better for certain types of targets.

A more detailed account of the performance of individual groups could also be yielded by looking at which group is more successful at predicting medium quality interfaces (recall and precision <50%) or accurate ones (those with recall and precision >50%). Thus, allowing the querying and grouping based on the recall and precision for the interfaces of models would allow this pattern to be observed more easily.

Most predictors try to optimally exploit biochemical information or any other nonstructural data that might be helpful. This is done either during the docking calculations by restricting the rigid body search to specific regions of the protein surface, or applying distance constraints, or by filtering candidate solutions output by

Milestone M24

the docking procedure. Having this information in the query would be helpful to distinguish models that benefit from pre-existing biochemical data.

Example of parameters to be queried based on participating groups:

Table I

Interface Prediction Statistics of Top Performers, Results Derived from Models Submitted in the CAPRI Docking Experiments

Predictor group	# Correct interfaces	# Total interfaces	# CAPRI targets	Fraction correct interfaces
Bonvin	245	420	21	0.5833
Zacharias	207	420	21	0.4929
Weng	192	420	21	0.4571
Zou	120	280	14	0.4286
Ten Eyck	90	214	11	0.4206
Zhou	148	358	18	0.4134
Wolfson	156	400	20	0.3900
Vajda	163	420	21	0.3881
HADDOCK	106	280	14	0.3786
Vakser	126	362	19	0.3481

Table II

Interface Prediction Statistics of Top Performers, Results Derived from Models Submitted in the CAPRI Scoring Experiments

Scorer group	# Correct interfaces	# Total predicted interfaces	# CAPRI targets	Fraction correct interfaces
Zou	125	222	12	0.5631
Bonvin	176	318	17	0.5535
Bates	145	280	14	0.5179
Fernandez-Recio	146	302	16	0.4834
Weng	115	240	12	0.4792
Wang	139	300	15	0.4633

Source: (Lensink and Wodak, 2010)

Based on individual participant, users of the query system should be able to query based on (but not limited to) these criteria:

- Category of participant (Scorer or Predictor)
- Type of participant (Server or human)
- Total correct interfaces
- Number of total interfaces
- Number of CAPRI targets
- Percentage of correctly predicted interfaces
- Average fraction of correctly predicted interfaces (Fraction correct interfaces)
- Number of models submitted based on quality ('incorrect', 'acceptable', 'medium' and 'high-quality') for each participant
- Total number of submitted models per participant

Implementation plan

A parser will be written to capture the parameters and values from previous results of CAPRI rounds. This consist of results for 41 CAPRI rounds encompassing 130 targets, with no less than 30 participants on average for each round.

Subsequently, the backbone of the query system will be developed based on Apache Solr. Apache Solr is a web application built around Lucene, which would facilitate faceted searching, filtering, as well as providing an easy platform to directly produce XML/HTPP and JSON APIs. This means that users can query directly based on a URL, which would make integration into any web platform straightforward. Apache Solr also allows an easy way for data indexing and loading, which can be done through a web administration interface.

Milestone M24

In addition, Solr allows range queries, which would allow easy grouping of parameters to be queried, which would be particularly useful for queries involving numbers.

For this step, a Solr schema will be defined encompassing all the parameters that should be allowed to be queried, the data structures, and whether they are multivalued or not. The data from CAPRI results that have been parsed will then be indexed and loaded into the Solr server. The search interface configuration and design will then be developed and implemented.

References

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